

INDIA-TAJIKISTAN POLITICAL AND DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS IN PRESENT INTERNATIONAL SCENARIO

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The disintegration of the Soviet Union led to the independence of five Central Asian states who suddenly emerged into sovereign existence on the dismantling multi-nationality federation of the erstwhile Soviet Union.¹ On 21 December 1991, in a closed-door meeting in the old Communist Party headquarter in the city of Alma-Ata, eleven political leaders reached an agreement to end the existence of the USSR and finally it ceased to exist on 25th December 1991, helped to the emergence of Central Asia in world politics.

Emergence of Central Asia as the latest region of sovereign states on the global map opened prospects of distinct shift in power politics.² Central Asia under the Soviets were organised into five republics and continued in the same form as successor states after Soviet disintegration.³

The present state of Tajikistan was created during the Soviet rule in 1929 which brought economic and social benefits to Tajikistan. The Republic was created as part of the 'National Territorial Delimitation Program' of the Soviets. This was for the first time that the Tajik Republic was given definite borders and a name denoting majority ethnic group.⁴ Though Tajikistan got full national territorial status during the Soviet period, Tajik identity had formed in the 5th and 6th centuries, according to Soviet historians and the process was completed within the 10th century Samanid empire.⁵ Tajikistan became independent in 1991 as a result of the Soviet disintegration.

The movement towards independence began in February 1990, following the reports that Armenian refugees were to be settled in Dushanbe, the capital of Tajikistan. As a concession to the growing Tajik nationalism, the Supreme Soviet, on 25 August, 1990, adopted a declaration of sovereignty emphasizing the equality of all nationalities living in

Tajikistan. On 9 September 1991, Tajikistan declared independence from the Soviet Union.⁶ From its inception to the present century, Tajikistan experienced different rulers who ruled different periods and was influenced by the culture and administration of different rulers. In the post-independence period, Tajikistan adopted a secular and democratic constitution with presidential form of government. Though the constitution of the country has clearly prescribed the division of powers between the executive and legislature, however, in reality, president holds enormous powers.⁷

The Republic of Tajikistan since independence in 1991 is living through a period of national and state reconstruction, self-determination and political and economic integration into the world community.⁸ The birth of the state was followed by a widespread bloody conflict, one of the longest and most difficult on the territory of the former Soviet Union. It has become a constant feature in the life of the country and the Central Asian region as a whole and has greatly influenced the process of state formation in Tajikistan, the course and direction of transformation processes in its economy, its social and cultural life, and its foreign policy, including relations with the others countries and with the Russia federation.⁹ The conflict has slowed down the achievement of full statehood in Tajikistan. As a result, Olimov points out, till the late 1990s, the national security concept has could not be fully determined, national interests were not identified, foreign policy priorities were not set, and the mechanism for the establishment and implementation of foreign policy was not been worked out.¹⁰

The establishment of foreign policy is impeded by constant changes taking place in the balance of political forces in the international arena and in the structure of geo-political and regional ties. The situation is far from settling down and each Central Asian state including Tajikistan is searching for its place in the new system of international relations.¹¹

In particular, in respect of India, Tajikistan is keen to develop warm, friendly and cooperative relations. The basic attitude of India towards Tajikistan has always been one of goodwill and equality. Both sides have nurtured their relations through the ages. Tajikistan is in India's extended neighbourhod, and is a geo-politically significant country. Indo-Tajik friendship is underlined by civilizational connect, economic and cultural 'give and take', people-to-people contact, and common regional interest and threats. The two countries have developed robust diplomatic contacts.¹²

The history of relations between India and Tajikistan is as old as the evolution of human civilization in the two regions. The people of the two regions are strongly inclined

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towards each other. The Republic of India is very much interested to build the traditional, cultural, political and economic ties by taking concrete steps towards the development of a more meaningful friendship and cooperation.

The relationship between India and Tajikistan has always been a smooth one since the time of Tajikistan's creation as an independent republic after the disintegration of the Soviet Union. Tajikistan's geo-political importance has induced both the sides to chart out their policies and relationship carefully and very smoothly.

India-Tajikistan relations have undergone various phases of emotional attachments understanding political reality, metamorphosis of economic ties in the light of respective economic compulsions and subsequently an integrationist approach with a view to bringing about an enriching culture of reconciliation, economic prosperity and regional peace. Both the countries share a common perspective on various issues, such as threat of Islamic fundamentalism, national separatism and cross-border terrorism which constitute the main threats to regional security, stability and development of both the regions.

India-Tajik contacts have been traditionally characterized by a clear prevalence of precisely the economic component. The migration of various groups to the Indian subcontinent over the centuries through or directly from the territory of present day Tajikistan, unification of the Tajik and Indian regions within the same states and even the rule in the South Asian Delhi Sultanate of the ethnic Tajik Gurid dynasty could not compare in terms of significance with the role of the cultural-civilizational and economic trade cooperation between both sides.¹³ Several researchers believe that this cooperation began as early as the Upper Paleolithic Age when the first economic relations arose between the bearers of the archeological cultures of south Tajikistan and North-West India.¹⁴ During the Bronze Age, the northern trade route of the cities of the Harappa, Indus Valley Civilization passed through Badakhshan; and a Harappa trade colony- the site of the ancient town of Shortgai A- was discovered on the south banks of the Panj.¹⁵

In the Soviet period, India regarded the Tajik SSR both as an example of the Soviet Union's economic achievements in Central Asia and as an ethnically and politically kindred Asian region. As long as the Central Asian republics were part of the USSR, India's relations with them were routed through Moscow but their Asian nature was noticed.¹⁶

India to a great extent than other Central Asian states, associates Tajikistan both with the aggravated threats to its internal and inter-regional political security and with the ways to eliminate these threats. An analysis of the works of Indian authors that appeared during the

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1990s shows that the Indian side followed the events in Tajikistan associated with the civil war quite closely and even with some apprehension. In so doing, India was generally on the side of the secular regimes. India clearly supported and approved of the end of the war and, most important, the way it ended.¹⁷ Again, India regarded Tajikistan as a state with potentially negative predominance of the Islamic component in everyday life. As in Tajikistan, Islam remains a strong factor which is also generally associated with India's overall idea about ensuring security in the Central Asian region and throughout Central and South Asia although it deserves a separate look.¹⁸

At present, India-Tajikistan bilateral relations are based on mutual respect, convergence of interests and similarity of views. Moreover, India and Tajikistan does not have any differences on any particular issue which needs to be resolved. Tajikistan has consistently extended support to India in the United Nations and in various UN forums. On the Jammu and Kashmir issue, Tajikistan holds the view that it is a bilateral dispute and may be resolved amicably by India and Pakistan.¹⁹

Furthermore, India hopes that Tajikistan remains stable, secular and friendly. However, external factors like instability in Afghanistan do pose a threat to secularism, political stability and democratic principles in Tajikistan. Instability in Afghanistan has its direct repercussions in neighbouring Tajikistan. India, no doubt, takes cognizance of these facts in developing its bilateral cooperation with Tajikistan.²⁰

Indo-Tajik Relations : The Issue of International Terrorism

India and Tajikistan together have been playing a positive role in the reconstruction of Afghanistan which has been the breeding ground for international terrorists and religious extremist forces ably supported by their counterparts in Pakistan and Saudi Arabia. Both countries have underlined the need to further strengthen secular and democratic ideas in international relations. In this regard, they are coordinating their efforts through a Joint Working Group (JWG) on combating international terrorism.²¹ Both the countries emphasize the need for an early conclusion of the comprehensive convention on combating international terrorism at the United Nations sponsored by India and supported by Tajikistan. The two countries share common values such as secularism, tolerance and strong opposition to the forces of fundamentalism and terrorism.²² Tajikistan has condemned the terrorist attacks in Mumbai and Srinagar. Deputy Foreign Affairs Minister of Tajikistan, Abdullo Uldoshev said,

“Tajikistan and India are facing common threats from terrorists and it would be our efforts to evolve common responses.”²³

Indo-Tajik cooperation would be an important part of the international coalition against religious extremism and international terrorism. Tajikistan has been an active supporter of India’s constructive initiatives in the reconstruction of Afghanistan.²⁴ Dushanbe has supported the Indian point of view on various regional and global issues and extends full support to India’s bid for permanent membership at the United Nations Security Council (UNSC).²⁵ The country also supports for peaceful resolution of all bilateral disputes between New Delhi and neighbouring countries.

India has been trying to build a solid edifice of bilateral relations based on the vast fund of goodwill at the popular level. In 1991-92, when heads of states from several important Asian and West European countries as well as the Foreign Secretaries of Britain and the US were rushing to the capitals of newly independent Central Asian states, New Delhi was content to send her junior Ministers of Commerce and External Affairs.²⁶

Political and Diplomatic Relations

So far as political and diplomatic factor is concerned, the Republic of India was one of the first foreign countries which recognized independence of a new country in the Central Asia, the Republic of Tajikistan and on August 28, 1992, an agreement was signed on the establishment of diplomatic ties between India and Tajikistan. After one year, the Republic of India opened its embassy in Tajikistan. The Republic of Tajikistan opened its diplomatic mission in August 2004 and in April 2006, appointed Ambassador of the Republic of Tajikistan in the Republic of India.²⁷ Since the independence, the Republic of Tajikistan has clear and peaceful foreign policy with priorities of the principle of transparency, fairness and multilevels.²⁸

Ever since the independence of the Republic of Tajikistan, both countries have exchanged high level visits from both sides. During the visits, both have laid the foundation for a mutually beneficial relationship in many areas such as, trade, defence, politics, energy cooperation, culture and development.²⁹

The political dialogue between India and Tajikistan has been regular and mutually beneficial. High-level exchanges have set the tempo to chart-out the scope and direction of cooperation and have also laid the foundation for understanding each other’s interests and core concerns. Both countries subscribe to common principles of inter-state conduct, peaceful

settlement of all differences and rejection of extremism of all forms as well as the principle of non-interference in the internal affairs of other countries.³⁰

The first major step in the direction of strengthening bilateral relations between India and Tajikistan was taken during the state visit of the then Tajik Prime Minister Abdul Mallik Abdullajanov in February 1993. The Tajik Prime Minister pledged to forge bonds of friendship and economic cooperation in the interest of peace and stability in the region and signed six agreements to give substance to their cooperation. The prime ministers of the two countries dwelled at length on the problems created by religious extremism and fundamentalism and also cross-border terrorism sponsored by the state to destabilise governments.³¹ In 1993, Indo-Central Asia relations wrote a new chapter when India's then Prime Minister, P.V. Narasimha Rao paid an official visit to the Central Asian republics of Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Kazakhstan. The first Central Asian visit in the post-Soviet period by the Indian Prime Minister unfortunately had to skip Tajikistan on account of the disturbed conditions there due to the bloody civil war.³² Despite valid reasons for Indian prime minister not being able to visit Tajikistan on account of the prevailing political instability in this republic until the signing of the Moscow Peace Accord (MPA) in 1997, the delay particularly after the success of the peace process had not been appreciated by the Tajik people at large who are quite enthusiastic about further deepening their age-old bonds of friendship.³³

Like Tajikistan, India also shares her strategic perception with Russia and the US regarding the spillover of Islamic fundamentalism from Afghanistan into Tajikistan. Therefore, it has urged both the Tajik Government and the Opposition to strive for political reconciliation.³⁴ However, it is also cognizant of the fact that Afghanistan's Hizb-e-Islami leader Gulbuddin Hekmatyar has had long-standing relations with the IRP of Tajikistan and with other Islamic parties in the region.³⁵

While India had been urged by Russia to play a role in the UN-mediated inter-Tajik talks, the former has not been keen as it would legitimize Pakistan's role in the conflict. India sees the threat to Tajikistan as a threat to the CIS and Russia.³⁶ In fact, the Indian Government has drawn some forced parallels between the situation in the Indian-held Kashmir and the border threat to Tajikistan from Afghanistan, mainly religious fundamentalism, violence and cross-border interventions.³⁷ More significantly, India wants to counter the efforts made by some Islamic countries, including Pakistan, to cultivate good relations with Tajikistan on the basis of religious affinity.³⁸

Tajik president's visit to India

Indo-Tajik relations reached at its height after the first state visit of president of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon took place in December 1995. It was preceded by the visit of the then Indian Minister of State for External Affairs, Salmon Khurshid to Tajikistan in June 1994. The visit further strengthened mutual understanding between India and Tajikistan of the situation in the neighbouring Afghanistan where the Mujahideen were creating trouble along the border of Tajiksitan.³⁹ The visit also resulted in signing another six agreements and one Memorandum of Understanding (MOU). These agreements related to the development of friendly ties for comprehensive of strengthening the cooperation between the two countries including cooperation at the international forums for setting up Indo-Tajik Joint Commission for Economic, Scientific and Technological Cooperation, protection of bilateral investment, cultural exchange programme, Memorandum of Understanding in environmental protection, cooperation in Science and Technology and in the area of health care.⁴⁰

On January 22, 1999, on his return journey from Vietnam, the President of Tajikistan, Emomali Rahmon made a brief halt at Delhi and had a meeting with Atal Behari Vajpayee, the Prime Minister of India, in which they discussed the problems of mutual cooperation between the two neighbouring states, the situation in the region etc.⁴¹

India-Tajikistan relations cemented further following the state visit of Tajik President Emomali Rahmon to India in May 2001. The visit resulted in signing of five agreements on mutual-legal assistance in criminal matters, on prevention of illicit trafficking in narcotics, on long-term cooperation in the field of industry, MOU on technical cooperation and agreement of direct air services between Dushanbe and New Delhi, besides a Joint Declaration on Principle of Mutual Relations (JDPMR).⁴² In the Tajik-Indian talks, the India's Prime Minister Mr. Atal Behari Vajpayee described Joint Tajik-Indian action as a "stabilizing factor" for the region. Vajpayee also noted that the state visit of the Tajik President had opened up a new chapter in 'close and dynamic' Tajik-Indian relations of friendship and cooperation oriented towards 21st century.⁴³

Cultural Relations

Cultural ties constitute an important pillar of the India-Tajikistan relationship. The Cultural Exchange Programme (CEP) for 2006-2009 signed during the Tajik President's visit would help in further expanding and strengthening cultural exchanges between New Delhi and Dushanbe.⁴⁴

Cultural cooperation between the two countries at an excellent level of regular of cultural troupes. In recent years, there has been strengthening of the Tajik-Indian cultural cooperation, which undoubtedly contributes to the overall climate of constructive bilateral relations, developing trade and economic ties, the traditional culture of mutual interests to the spiritual heritage of both countries. Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR) sent the third batch of teachers for the cultural centre of ICCR, including teachers of dance and tabla.⁴⁵

The friendly relations with former Soviet Union positively influenced the attitudes of Tajik people towards India and its culture, which continues to manifest in the popularity of Indian movies, dance, music and yoga in Tajikistan. The two countries signed a programme of cooperation in the field of culture for the year 2012-2015 during President Rahmon's visit to India in September 2012. An Indian Cultural Centre (ICC) attached to the Embassy was officially inaugurated on 30th June, 2003. Besides regular dance and music classes, the ICCR conducts yoga and Hindi classes as well, which have become quite popular.⁴⁶

The Cultural Centre of India attached to Embassy at Dushanbe has also made weighty contribution to the development of cultural relations between Tajikistan and India. On the initiative of this centre attached to the embassy six month's courses for studying Hindi language are organized. The centre regularly organizes scientific conferences, lectures, seminars, meetings etc., in which the leading scholars of India and Tajikistan take part.⁴⁷ Just in the year 2000-2001, several conferences and seminars were held here, including the conference on "Synthesis of Sufism and Indian Culture" on November 18, 2000 and the seminars on "Indian Style" on April 27, 2001, on "communication revolution in India" on August 9, and another conference on "Yoga- The Indispensable System of Health and Joy" on September 16.⁴⁸

At present, a cultural and enlightenment centre called "Lamp of Life" is functioning at the Kandil Juraev Tajik Pedagogical University in the city of Dushanbe. In the premises of this Centre, there is a permanent exhibition "The World of Khayam" along with a corner "Khayam in India". This centre intends to organise various programmes dedicated to the issues of the history of philosophy of India.⁴⁹

There are several indications of favourable public opinion of India and thereby India's soft power leverage in Tajikistan. A recent public opinion survey conducted by the Tajik think tank Sharq Research Centre (SRC) found a majority of respondents harbour very friendly attitudes towards India.⁵⁰ Positive perceptions of India can further be inferred by the 600 plus Indian films that are dubbed into the Tajik language.⁵¹ Much of this translation is

possible, because several of the universities in Tajikistan have strong Hindi and Urdu departments, indicating the existence of a deeper scholarly interest in India and the demand for Indian languages in Tajikistan.⁵²

Similarly, the works of Indian writers such as Rabindranath Tagore, Prem Chand and others were translated into Tajik. Even Tagore became a familiar name throughout the former Soviet Union, including in Tajikistan.⁵³ There is also evidence of the common history in India, for example, the grave of the famous 17th century Tajik poet Abdul Qadir Bedil in Central Delhi. Again, to further the interest in Indian culture and history among the Tajik people, the Indian Embassy in Dushanbe regularly organizes celebrations of the festivals of Holi, Diwali and the birthday of Mahatma Gandhi.⁵⁴

Thus, all those above steps will help to further the future relations between the two sides as that will become far more widespread and stronger and serve the cause of peace and cooperation.

Vajpayee's Visit to Tajikistan : A Big Boost to Indo-Tajik Relations

India-Tajikistan relations wrote a new chapter when India's then Prime Minister Atal Behari Vajpayee paid a goodwill visit to the Republic of Tajikistan on November 13, 2003. It was the first-ever visit by an Indian prime minister to Tajikistan since the country obtained independence on September 9, 1991. Tajikistan has opened its embassy in New Delhi which strengthened her relationship with the latter. During his stay, prime minister Vajpayee met the Tajik President Emomali Rahmon, and the Prime Minister Akil Akilov.

During prime minister Vajpayee's visit, both the Indian prime minister and Tajik president Rahmon called for increasing trade and commercial relations between the two countries. India announced a special financial package of \$40 million for Tajikistan which included a credit line of \$ 25 million for the infrastructure development in Tajikistan.⁵⁵

The two sides also agreed to extend road links from the Iranian Port of Chabahar through Afghanistan into Tajikistan and set up a Joint Working Group on counter-terrorism. The signing of a Joint working Group on counter terrorism would help in combating International Terrorism, Organised Crime, Money Laundering and Illegal Trafficking in weapons.⁵⁶

New Delhi and Dushanbe decided to intensify defence cooperation between the two republics and signed agreements for this purpose. The other agreements signed included an extradition treaty, the setting up of an Indo-Tajik Information Technology Centre (ITITC) and an accord on tourism cooperation. At the end of the visit of Tajikistan Republic, Mr.

Vajpayee stressed that “our relationship in the present day is built on a shared commitment to democracy, secularism and the rule of law. We have common concerns in the region.”⁵⁷

Prime Minister Vajpayee’s visit to Tajikistan was not only timely, but productive and substantial at this juncture. India and Tajikistan reaffirmed to strengthen their strategic cooperations. Both the countries committed to add new areas of emphasis. Such moves speak of the urgency of taking bilateral ties to new heights in the changing world order.

Again, Tajik President Emomali Rahmon visited New Delhi during August 6-10, 2006 on a state visit at the invitation of India’s Prime Minister. Dr. Manmohan Singh. The visit was preceded by the meeting of the bilateral Inter-Governmental Commission (IGC) and India-Tajikistan Joint Working Group (ITJWG) meeting on counter terrorism both held in New Delhi.⁵⁸ This visit of the Tajik president gave great impulse on Tajik-Indian relations.

Tajikistan’s parliamentary delegation also visited India, senior expert group from Ministry of Defence, Energy Company of Tajikistan “Barki Tojik”, Academy of Sciences and others. From Indian side, senior officials of the Government of India visited Tajikistan.⁵⁹

On August 28, 2007, the Republic of Tajikistan and the Republic of India noted to celebrate 15-years of establishment of Tajik-Indian diplomatic relations. These two countries historically linked by long-standing tradition of close cooperation and friendship between the people, deep cross-cultural relations. Under the new statehood of the Republic of Tajikistan relations between countries moved to a new stage of development.⁶⁰ In its foreign policy, the Republic of Tajikistan pays special attention to the Tajik-Indian relations based on close cooperation and mutual understanding between the two countries. The two countries have developed a strong framework for strengthening and developing bilateral relations.

Similarly, in September 2009, India’s then President, Mrs. Pratibha Patil paid a three-day goodwill visit to Tajikistan which was the first ever visit by an Indian President to the Central Asian region. On the occasion, she attended the National Day celebrations of Tajikistan as the Guest of Honour. During her visit, president Patil held talks with her Tajik counterpart, Imomali Rahmon on a wide range of issues, including efforts to tackle terrorism, bilateral relations and developments in and around the region, aimed at consolidating ties between the two countries in the political, economic and other spheres.⁶¹ Besides, Patil also held meetings with the Tajik Prime Minister, the Foreign Minister and the Defence Minister of Tajikistan and interacted with the Chairman and members of the Lower House of the Tajik Parliament.⁶² Although no bilateral official document was signed during president Patils’ visit, the significance of her visit lies in India’s efforts to accord a more prominent position to

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Tajikistan in its foreign policy priorities.⁶³ The visit is indicative of Tajikistan's critical importance for India and the importance of enhancing mutual goodwill, trust and confidence. India and Tajikistan have maintained the tradition of close political understanding and mutual cooperation.⁶⁴ Thus, the visit of Indian President Patil to Tajikistan sends a powerful signal to the existence of bilateral relations.

Similarly, India's then External Affairs Minister SM Krishna visited Tajikistan on July 2-3, 2012. His visit to Dushanbe was the first by an Indian External Affairs Minister to this strategically located country. He was received by Tajik president Emomali Rahmon to the country and his visit gave an impetus to the friendly relations and multi-dimensional cooperation between the two countries.⁶⁵ SM Krishna held extensive discussions with the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Tajikistan, Hamrokhon Zarifi, about bilateral cooperation on several issues, including energy, counter-terrorism and communication aimed at further cementing bilateral ties.⁶⁶

Also, a constructive talk was held regarding the international and regional issues of both countries. Including in the framework of the United Nations Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), concerning the strengthening of peace and stability in Afghanistan, as well as the development of economic-trade cooperation through the territory of this country.⁶⁷ During his visit, Krishna extended to Imomali Rahmon the invitation of the president and prime minister of India for paying an official visit to this country which will give an impetus to the friendly relations and will be the milestone for further strengthening of historical ties between the two countries.

President Rahmon's Visit to India : A Fresh Impetus for Indo-Tajik Relations

India-Tajikistan relations received a fresh impetus during the state visit of president Imomali Rahmon to India from 1-4 September 2012 at the invitation of the president of the Republic of India, His Excellency Mr. Pranab Mukherjee. This is Tajik president Rahmon's fifth visit to India as his earlier visits to this country were in 1995, 1999, 2001 and 2006. In New Delhi, Tajik President Mr. Imomali Rahmon held detailed discussions with the then prime minister of India, Dr. Manmohan Singh and met the president of Republic of India, and Vice-President Hamid Ansari on September 3, 2012.⁶⁸

President Rahmon's visit has not only strengthened existing ties, but has also resulted in building a long-term strategic partnership. According to the joint statement issued during his visit, India and Tajikistan have "decided to elevate their bilateral relations to the level of a long-term strategic partnership".⁶⁹ This strategic partnership is expected to increase

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cooperation in a wide spectrum of areas- political, economic health, human resources development, defence, counter-terrorism, science and technology, culture and tourism etc.⁷⁰ President Rahmon's visit can be analyzed in the context of the trajectory of the India-Tajikistan relationship and the concrete outcomes which are expected to result from the new strategic partnership agreement inked between the two countries.⁷¹

The Indian side noted that the visit of the President Rahmon was a welcome continuation of the tradition of regular exchange of high level visits between India and Tajikistan. The two countries reviewed the current status of bilateral relations and exchanged views on regional and international issues. They noted the similarity of their positions on bilateral, regional and global issues.⁷² Both sides agreed that the Foreign Ministries and other line Ministries of both countries would continue to hold regular consultations, including exchange of visits. They noted with satisfaction that the discussions took place in a warm and friendly atmosphere.⁷³ The visit also testified to the close historical and deep cultural ties between the two countries.

Indo-Tajik Relations : A Big Commitment to Multilateralism

Both India and Tajikistan expressed their strong commitment to multilateralism, with the United Nations playing a central role in dealing with global challenges and threats.⁷⁴ They reaffirmed their commitment to the reform of the United Nations, particularly, the Security Council, through its expansion in the permanent and non-permanent categories, with increased representation of developing countries in both, in order to improve its efficiency, representativeness, and legitimacy to meet contemporary challenges faced by the international community.⁷⁵ The Tajik side reiterated its support for India's candidature for permanent membership of an expanded Security Council.⁷⁶

Further, Indo-Tajik relations got big boost when India's then Vice-President Mr. Hamid Ansari paid an extremely productive four-day visit to Middle East nations in April, 2013. Mr. Ansari said that this visit was his first ever visit to Tajikistan and held that besides the substance of his discussions with the Tajik leadership, headed by its president Imomali Rahmon, the general ambience and warmth displayed by his hosts was "very significant" in the field of international diplomacy.⁷⁷ Ansari's visit is a part of India's "Connect Central Asia Policy", aimed at greater political, economic and people-to-people engagement with Central Asian nations including Tajikistan.⁷⁸

In September 2014, India's then External Affairs Minister, Smt. Sushma Swaraj visited Tajikistan for the Council of Heads of Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO)

Summit, held in Dushanbe. The prime minister of the Republic of India, His Excellency, Mr. Narendra Modi paid a state visit to the Republic of Tajikistan from 12 to 13 July, 2015, at the invitation of the president of the Republic of Tajikistan, His Excellency Mr. Imomali Rahmon. The president and the prime minister held wide-ranging talks on bilateral regional and international issues. The discussions between the leaders were warm and cordial and the outcomes of the visit reflected the mutual trust that exists between the two countries.⁷⁹ Both leaders expressed satisfaction at the excellent relations between India and Tajikistan. They noted that ties between the two countries are based on shared history and cultural affinity between their people and reaffirmed their commitment to take all necessary steps to transform bilateral relations into a multi-faceted strategic partnership for the mutual benefits of the people of both the countries.⁸⁰ Both sides welcomed continuing exchanges at Ministerial and Senior Official levels which serve to cement bilateral ties. Prime Minister Modi expressed appreciation at Tajikistan's efforts at curbing extremism and radicalism and to ensure secular governance which is a common ideal of both the countries.⁸¹

Also, both leaders emphasized the centrality of cultural interactions in further deepening the close bonds between the peoples of India and Tajikistan. They called for active implementation of the programme of cooperation between India and Tajikistan and Art and Culture for the period 2016-18 and agreed that relevant organisations hold "Days of Culture" in each other's country.⁸² The leaders expressed their happiness at the excellent cooperation between the two countries on multilateral issues and mutual support for their initiatives in the United Nations and other international forums. Modi thanked Tajikistan for its support in declaring June 21 as "International Day of Yoga" in the United Nations and for successful organisation of events to mark the occasion in Dushanbe and other regions of Tajikistan.⁸³ India's Prime Minister expressed deep gratitude to President Rahmon for the warm welcome and the gracious hospitality extended during his visit to Tajikistan.

Again, in December, 2016, Tajik president Imomali Rahmon paid a goodwill visit to India. During his visit, he was accorded a ceremonial welcome by president Pranab Mukherjee at Rashtrapati Bhavan. He also held wide-ranging talks with Prime Minister Modi on bilateral, regional and international issues, before the two leaders issued a joint statement. India's Prime Minister in his address, called Tajikistan "a valued friend and strategic partner" and appreciated Rahmon's leadership and contribution in strengthening bilateral relationship.⁸⁴

In July 2018, India's Prime Minister Narendra Modi visited to five Central Asian countries – Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. This visit was as Indian diplomats said, aimed at making India a strong player in a region rich in natural resources and important strategically, especially in the fight against terrorism.⁸⁵ On October 12, 2018, India's Hon'ble External Affairs Minister Smt. Sushma Swaraj, attended the SCO Heads of Council of Ministers meeting in Dushanbe. While addressing the meeting, Smt. Swaraj expressed India's support for open, stable international trade regime based on centrality of the World Trade Organisation (WTO). Earlier addressing the Indian community and Tajik Friends of India at a cultural event organised by the Embassy of India on October 11, 2018, Smt. Swaraj spoke of the close cultural bonds between Tajikistan and India and the shared ethos of strong family values.⁸⁶

In October 2018, India's President Ram Nath Kovind paid state visit to Tajikistan. In his very first visit to Central Asia after assuming office, president Ram Nath Kovind met President of Tajikistan Imomali Rahmon in Dushanbe. While recalling the long-standing diplomatic relations with Tajikistan, India's president said, "India and Tajikistan together have built a strong foundation for bilateral and multilateral cooperation. In 2012, we elevated our relationship to the level of strategic parenthood".⁸⁷ He also said that India will remain committed to providing assistance support to Tajikistan. Taking the ties forward, the Indian president signed Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) in the fields of political relations, strategic research, agriculture, renewable energy, traditional medicine, space technology, youth affairs, cultural and disaster management.⁸⁸ President Kovind also appreciated the commendable work done by Tajikistan to tackle the global menace of terrorism and foster peace for one and all.⁸⁹ He also went to Ayni where he was received by Commander of India Contingent and visited the museum. Both presidents agreed to work for strategic cooperation between the two countries.⁹⁰

Thus, both India and Tajikistan should continue a comprehensive dialogue and cooperation programmes on all aspects of mutual concern and benefits. A new mechanism to enhance the mutual relationship and cooperation needs to be formulated a regular intense dialogue between the leaderships of two countries could help forge closer understanding and cooperation.

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